

Designing, Pilot-Testing, and Implementing the Brahmavākya Module as a Tool for Religious Nonviolent Peacebuilding

(With Reference to Ancient India's Jain, Buddhist, and Hindu Meditation Texts on Soteriology)

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[Condensed Abstract]

This study investigates the dual role of religion in both inciting conflict and fostering nonviolent peacebuilding. Drawing upon ancient Indian meditation texts from the Jain, Buddhist, and Hindu traditions, it outlines the conceptual evolution and empirical operationalization of *Brahmavākya*—a composite construct that synthesizes the dimensions of repentance, ethical conduct, meditation, generosity, and truthfulness. Through the following sequential steps: (1) the design of the Brahmavākya Module, (2) its pilot-testing and implementation, (3) the evaluation of its outcomes, and (4) benchmarking against global best practices followed by iterative redesign, this study demonstrates how ancient religious wisdom can be translated into actionable strategies for nonviolent peacebuilding. The findings have significant implications for curriculum development, interfaith dialogue, and public policy. The study concludes with recommendations for future research in the field of peace and conflict studies.

Key Words

Social issues in India, structural violence, religious violence, terrorism, communal conflict, Jain soteriology, Buddhist soteriology, Hindu soteriology, comparative soteriology, Brahmavākya, peace education, nonviolence, pilot-testing, impact evaluation, and policy suggestions
